

DESTINATION CENTRAL DISTRICT: THE REPRESENTATION OF THE CONFLICT.

ABSTRACT

Purpose – The main aim of this paper is to represent the conflict of touristification in the central district of Seville to evaluate the dimension of the problem. Therefore, it focuses on the diagnostic representation of the conflict between citizens and tourists, to help define the coexistence of conflicting interests and to bring solutions in favour of a liveable urban landscape.

Design/methodology/approach – The research has implied a detailed analysis beyond the observation data and statistics, which facilitated a complex diagnosis for decision making. This has led to consider as an initial framework the main tourist resources, official agreements and civil manifestations regarding touristification. Then, factors of tourist density and one in-depth case study of changes in use have been mapped.

Findings – Firstly, an analysis of the urban spaces affected by the tourist dynamics following the degree of habitability of the resident citizens have been led. Secondly, of the conflict resulting from a relationship between economic activities, the attractiveness of the urban landscape and the tourist use of the space has been mapped.

Originality/value – Through the study of the central district of a city of great heritage value where conflicts begin to occur as a result of tourism, it is intended to contribute to the development of the spatial syntax of the tourist conflict, what could lead to improve responsible urban and social city policies.

Keywords: *tourist uses; liveability; touristification; urban conflict; mapping; Seville*

Paper type – *Research paper*

1. INTRODUCTION

The coexistence of the quality of life of citizens and the economic activity generated by tourism is creating in recent times a framework of social and political concern (Yang *et al.*, 2013). In this case, refer to the tourism of agglomeration, congregation and confluences in urban space, that have been extensively dealt with in recent scientific publications (Romero-Padilla *et al.*, 2019), which result of tension in coexistence, a growing alteration of uses and, consequently, the banalisation of part of the city's neighbourhoods.

There is a progressive increase in the movement of national and international tourists. A general picture of this dynamic is shown by the data provided by the United Nations World Tourism Organization in terms of annual flow: in 2010 there was a movement of international tourist arrivals of 952 million, in 2015 of 1,197 and in 2019 of 1,461 million, of which 51% arrived in Europe affecting the main capitals and cities.

This phenomenon, originally linked to beach or monumental destinations, has steadily extended to large urban areas through combining the traditional tourist resources with leisure, entertainment and other urban uses (Sassen and Roost, 1999). Within this framework, the negative consequences on local inhabitants have started revealing a conflict that, in the beginning, was particularly dense in coastal areas (Aledo, Ortuño and Jimeno, 2017) as well as large urban centres and metropolises (Mansilla López, 2018). Nevertheless, the generalization of heritage-based tourism on historical cities (Calle Vaquero, 2002) has quickly expanded to many European and Mediterranean areas with a tradition of cultural tourism industries (Cànoves, G, Prat & Blanco, 2016), accommodation and gastronomic offer, encouraging competition based on urban and heritage marketing (Murray Mas, 2014). That is the case of Andalusia (Moreno Navarro, 2019). Tourist activity is considered a fundamental engine in the regional economy, representing 12.8% in terms of income. In the business activities of cities, this translates into demand for goods and services catalysing the productive system of the Andalusian economy, in which relationships are created between the different economic sectors involved in the production, either directly or indirectly. The Strategic Tourism Marketing Plan Horizon 2020 of Andalusia marks as a priority strategy the increase in the number of tourists, estimating the desired growth between 3.5% and 5%. Thus, the official data for 2019 estimate that more than 32 million tourists have visited the Andalusian territory, which represents an increase of 5.9% over the previous year according to the Institute of Statistics of Andalusia. Certainly, expectations have been exceeded by reality resulting in urban and social conflicts.

In cities such as Seville, the capital of Andalusia, the local administration is reacting in different directions and intensities by focusing, firstly, its efforts on alleviating the alleged accommodation activities on a first level and, secondly, the disturbance generated by noise in public space. As a result, the urban

mutation suffered by the areas with the greatest intensity of tourists, transforming proximity into tourist services and affecting the residents' liveability, has been neglected. In this scenario, we focus on Seville, due to its heritage, cultural and leisure attractions (Díaz-Parra & Jover, 2018) which represent a focus of massive interest. The historic centre of Seville has traditionally been a particularly wide and dense area in terms of local activities, social life and public spaces with a deep sense of community (Cantero, Escalera, García del Villar & Hernández, 1999). These spaces are assuming a greater intensity of economic activity, mainly developed in public space, affecting the resident population in their well-being and coexistence, in addition to suffering multiple impacts of different magnitudes: specialization of economic activity, alteration of rest, decline in the diversity of urban space, increase in price and transformation of neighbourhood commerce, etc.

Added to the effects produced by the change in lifestyle and the gentrification of the central areas, Recently, the over-pressure of tourism has translated into a growth in economic activities for visitors - leisure and restaurants- (Jover & Díaz-Parra, 2020), thus displacing other less lucrative but necessary activities that should serve the residents whose impact is starting to be addressed by official documents as the Seville City Council's publication on the concentration of areas acoustically saturated by leisure and restaurant activity in the Central District (Urbanismo Sevilla, 2019).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A review of the theoretical bases and recent academic discussions reveals that the current conflict over the tourist space stems from a double problematic. On the one hand, the impact of marketing techniques applied to urban policies that justified tourist development in many big cities (Harvey, 1989) will end up affecting heritage tourism by reinforcing a vicious circle that was already present in the lack of understanding between the management of tourism and that of heritage assets (Russo, 2002). This process, transferred to the so-called "new cultural policies" (Bianchini, 1993), has affected the social conditions of its inhabitants (Benach, 2016).

On the other hand, the spatial conflict that derives from a transformation in the traditional forms of tourism (Domínguez & Russo, 2010) towards the establishment of semi-permanent residents in central historical areas of the city (Huete & Mantecón, 2010). This gives rise to a new form of occupation and displacement of the traditional social fabric (Sequera & Nofre, 2018), which can no longer be called gentrification or, according to some authors such as Aalbers (2019) would be the fifth wave of gentrification.

This new transformation is closely related to the so-called ‘Airbnb phenomenon’ -named after the main web platform that allows owners and users to respectively advertise their accommodations and search for available options according to their preferences- which has become one of the hot spots in the social debate on touristification and has quickly reached the academic sphere with a good number of recent publications (Sequera & Nofre, 2019; Cocola-Gant & Gago, 2019) that analyse, among other aspects, the space conflict caused by their proliferation, the phenomenon of generalization of real estate speculation, which becomes a transnational and transversal process between social classes, the consequences in the substitution or elimination of the inhabitants in historical neighborhoods, or their urban impacts at a global level, both in large metropolises such as Barcelona (Arias & Quagliari, 2016) and in more remote places or places with a rural tradition that have, however, begun to visibly suffer their effects (Yrigoy, 2017). Among the diverse consequences that have negatively affected the local population resident in the central districts (Fernández Tabales & Santos Pavón 2018), we cannot ignore one of the most burning issues at present, which updates the traditional conflict between social reality, local traditions and the real estate market (Carmona García, 2015): the large increase in the presence of rental housing for tourism purposes in certain urban areas, originally settled under the principles of sharing economy (Bani, 2017) but turned into one of the greatest great drivers of real estate speculation today. This has led to an increase in the price for the purchase or long-term rental (Casanova Fernando, 2019), with the consequent limitation of the right to housing for residents of historic areas, where gentrification processes have been amplified by hands of touristification (Jover & Díaz-Parra, 2019). This leads to a complex situation that, although it is rooted in a spatial problem, ultimately manifests as a social conflict that has been catalogued as overtourism with a multidimensional character (Zmyślony et al., 2020) and needs to be addressed with a perspective of sustainability, with valid interlocutors capable of mediating between the different stakeholders (Zmyślony & Kowalczyk - Anioł, 2019).

3. OBJECTIVES

Given the abovementioned, the main aim of this paper is to represent the conflict of touristification in the central district of Seville to evaluate the dimension of the problem. This representation will imply a detailed analysis beyond the observation data (direct and indirect) or statistics, and which facilitates a more adequate diagnosis for decision making.

Therefore, the present contribution focuses on the diagnostic representation of the conflict between citizens and tourists, having as a general objective, to help define the coexistence of conflicting interests and to bring, in the end, solutions in favour of a liveable urban landscape.

Furthermore, it is intended to contribute to the development of the spatial syntax of social, urban and cultural variables that provide dynamic cartographies of the different tensions present in the city for their solution.

4. METHODOLOGY

The proposed representation of the complex is based on a methodology built over the basic premise of the existence of a direct or indirect relationship between the urban space and the facts that take place in it. This paradigm, transferred to the object of study – the central district of the city of Seville, Spain -, is distilled into a series of variables that detect the conflict, making it visible through an operative methodology of spatial analysis, what implies the use of massive data from the local administration itself and its computation with tools of cartographic representation, as well as other data sources both public (like the regional and national statistics services) and private (open data and free mapping contributions). This has led to taking into account, as an initial framework, both the official agreements and the main civil manifestations of rejection of the process of touristification that has taken place in Seville in recent years. Besides, an analysis of the location, characterization and use of the tourist attractions that are most promoted from official sources has been carried out. Finally, the values that represent the tourist density in the central district have been represented along with an approach to one specific case study the mapping of changes in use.

Deepening into the representation of social and urban conflict, it has been based on obtaining primary data, its combination and analysis, for the preparation of representative cartography of the social conflict. All this generates results on four areas involved in the conflict that is necessary for the conceptualisation of the research: the heritage content of the city of Seville, the urban anatomy of the Old Town District, the presence of services and activities and the local regulatory framework. The choice of variables is based on data on the identification of the services and economic activities present that have a link with the figure of the tourist. To this, values related to habitability and signs of conflict have been added: catering establishments -shops, bars, restaurants or 24-hour food services- and accommodation -hotels, hostels and private lodgings-. In both cases, they are identified in the cadastral plots where the activity is located, thus generating a topology with the urban fabric. Finally, contextual variables have been defined based on the selection of indicators taken from the Special Plan of Environmental Sustainability Indicators for Urban Development Activity in Seville (Rueda, 2008). In defining the environment, demographic variables have been considered -average age, age groups and density of the resident population -, urban variables -the size of the residential plot, urban morphology, heritage content and proximity to public

spaces- and habitability variables -changes in use and activities that are lost and those that are replaced by new establishments-. In the analysis, GIS tools have been necessary for the definition, representation and generation of data topologies, and GEPHI 0.9.2 for the statistical treatment of the tourist/resident relationship and the representation of tensions in space. The analysis and data mining generate indicators of state and pressure on the resident population.

5. RESULTS

The research has focused on obtaining a faithful analysis of the urban spaces affected by the tourist dynamics under the degree of habitability of the resident citizens. In this sense, it has been obtained a representation of the conflict resulting from a relationship between economic activities, the attractiveness of the urban landscape and the tourist use of the space. Before this, data has been taken about both official and civil actions that have supported or limited the effects of tourism in the historical centre of the city of Seville.

5.1 Local tourism promotion in the central district in Seville

Before mapping the conflict of tourism, it will be necessary to study which areas are particularly sensitive to tourism pressure. To this end, we will begin by analysing which tourism resources are promoted with greater emphasis from the administration and local tourism offices. The data have been extracted from the official tourism website of the Seville City Council (Ayuntamiento de Sevilla, 2020) in the latest version available at the time of writing of this paper in February 2020.

The website is organized in six main sections: Things to do -with the main attractions of the city-, What's on -with the current cultural agenda-, Eating out -gastronomy and party plans-, Shopping -shops and crafts-, Useful info -for the trip and the stay-, and Plans -proposals and routes-.

Among them, we list below those express references to specific locations in the city: the monumental surroundings formed by the Cathedral(1), the Alcazar(2) and the Archivo de Indias(3), the Triana neighbourhood(4), the Fine Arts Museum(5), the Santa Cruz neighbourhood(6), the Aquarium(7), the María Luisa Park(8), the Church of El Salvador(9), the Maestranza bullring(10), Torre del Oro(11), San Bernardo neighbourhood(12), Isla de la Cartuja(13), Plaza de España(14), Plaza del Cabildo(15), Paseo de Colón(16), Alameda de Hércules(17), Maestranza Theatre(18), the Tobacco Factory(19), Paseo Marqués del Contadero(20), the Dueñas Palace(21), the Salinas House(22), the Hospital de la Caridad(23), the Casa de Pilatos(24), the Metropol Parasol(25), the historical centre(26), the CAAC(27),

the Navigation Pavilion(28), the CaixaForum(29), the House of Science(30), the Plaza de Armas(31), Miraflores Park(32), the Arenal district(33), the convents(34.1 to 34.29), Plaza del Duque(35), Sierpes and Tetuán streets(36), Plaza Nueva(37), Nervión(38), los Remedios(39), la Alfalfa(40) and la Encarnación districts(41), Los Arcos(42), Plaza de Armas(43), Nervión Plaza(44), El Corte Inglés(45), Lagoh(46) and Torre Sevilla(47) shopping centres, Triana(48), Encarnación(49), Arenal(50) and Lonja del Barranco(51) markets, San Telmo Palace(52), Sagrario Church(53), Archbishop's Palace(54), Hospital de los Venerables(55), Santa Cruz(56), Santa María la Blanca(57) and San Nicolás de Bari(58) churches, San José Chapel(59), Buen Suceso(60), and San Luis de los Franceses(61) churches, Casa de la Moneda(62), Biblioteca Colombina(63), Torre de la Plata(64), Arquillo de Mañara(65), Postigo del Aceite(66), Houses of los Pinelo(67), las Sirenas(68), la Provincia(69), los Bucarelli(70), los Mañara(71), los Padilla(72), of the Moorish King(73), Lissén(74), Palaces of the Countess of Lebrija(75), of the Pumarejo(76), Guardiola(77), Monastery(78), Altamira(79), Marquises of Algaba(80), Marquises of Villapanés(81), Monsalves(82), Pedro I(83), Yanduri(84) and Marquis of la Motilla(85).

In total, the official website of Tourism of Seville mentions 85 locations, of which 68 are located in the central district, that is, 80 per cent of the tourist resources of Seville are located in an area where currently lives 8.4% of the inhabitants of the city. The abovementioned tourist attractions located in the central district have been numbered and mapped in Figure 1.

5.2 Institutional and popular reactions to the conflict

Subsequently, it is necessary to situate the emergence and evolution of the conflict in time. To this end, we have listed the main events, whether promoted by local administrations, interest groups or citizens, which have evidenced the existence of tensions between local inhabitants and the increased presence of tourism (Milano, 2017) in the central district of Seville. To this end, a review has been carried out based mainly on newspaper library resources and news from official bodies, which will make it possible to reconstruct the evolution of this conflict in Seville (Villar Lama and Fernández Tabales, 2017).

We can point to the first institutional recognition of the pressure on tourist and residential spaces in the city centre in the 2013 declaration of Acoustically Saturated Areas of Seville, due mainly to the high presence of bars and leisure terraces, 4 of which are located in the central district (Urbanismo Sevilla, 2019). Later, the associations of hoteliers and owners of tourist accommodation have requested revisions in 2017 and 2019.

From the citizen's point of view, the first formal protest action against the tourist pressure took place in April 2018, with the constitution of the *Colectivo-Asamblea Contra la Turistización de Sevilla*

"CACTUS" (Cactus Seville, 2018), which collects and offers information about the problems derived from tourism that affect the inhabitants of the historical centre, and regularly organizes events in collaboration with other local groups and neighbourhood and tenant associations.

In the second half of 2018, the Seville City Council will begin to take measures to balance tourism development with the needs of the inhabitants of historic areas. The first milestone will be the launch during the summer of a citizen consultation for the possible regulation of tourist accommodation, whose proliferation was beginning to become a problem for the inhabitants (Ayuntamiento de Sevilla, 2018a). Even though the consultation was aimed at carrying out a specific modification of the General Urban Development Plan, this has not yet taken place.

In September 2018, the statutes of the Seville Tourism Agency were created and approved, with the participation, in addition to the City Council, of different bodies and civil agents representing tourism activity, the business fabric and citizens (Ayuntamiento de Sevilla, 2018b). A month later, in October, the Declaration of Good Practices of the Santa Cruz District was signed (ABC de Sevilla, 2018), which includes 18 measures to protect this area of the central district -one of the most monumental in the city- from excessive tourism. In December 2018, the Municipal Plan for Housing, Land and Rehabilitation of the Municipal District of Seville was published, with a specific section on the problems generated in housing by short-term rentals for tourist use (EMVISESA, 2019a).

However, the positioning of the city of Seville within the tourism industry would have its great impulse and positioning at a global level with the celebration, in April 2019, of the World Travel and Tourism Council in the city's Congress Palace with the participation of 1650 delegates from all over the world, including high political representatives and general managers of large multinational tourism companies (World Travel & Tourism Council, 2019).

As a citizen's reaction to the international macro event (Diario de Sevilla, 2019), in April 2019 took place the Social Meeting against Tourism: Alternatives and Resistances (ESTAR), promoted by CACTUS in collaboration with other citizen platforms in Seville (CACTUS Seville, 2019). The same association created, in September 2019, the platform of tenants of Seville to protect the inhabitants in rent regime of the excessive increases of the prices due to the increasing occupation of housings as tourist apartments. In October of the same year, the collective Zemos98 organised the Hackcamp "The city is ours" in Seville, which was devoted to the right to the city against the public appropriation of the symbols and spaces of the historic city, and which brought together designers and experts from different countries to create artistic actions for intervention in public space (Zemos98, 2019). More recently, in February 2020, posters in Spanish, English and Chinese containing "Ten Commandments" signed by "The Gentrified" have

appeared in some particularly tourist areas of the central district of Seville, some of which allude to the degradation produced by tourism in the city, housing and local ways of life (El Plural, 2020).

From the official bodies, in September 2019 the joint declaration for tourism in the city of Seville was signed, consisting of a decalogue signed by the City Council, the Confederation of Employers and the Chamber of Commerce (Europa Press, 2019). More recently, in December 2019, the Municipal Housing Company (EMVISESA) has published maps with the creation of the Rental Reference Price Index (IPRA) of Seville rental housing, which allows observing the tourist pressure on rental housing in the central district of Seville compared to other areas of the city (EMVISESA, 2019b).

5.3 Mapping the conflict: changes in use derived from tourism in the urban heritage fabric

Before the representation of the social conflict between citizen and tourist, a brief description of the demographic profile of the inhabitants of the Central District is made. Thus, the population of Seville in 2019 is unevenly distributed among the 11 districts in which the city is organized (Ayuntamiento de Sevilla, 2019). The Central District (called the Old Town) has a relatively large population compared to the total - 58,378 residents represent 9% of a total population of 669,005 inhabitants. With a density of 140 inhabitants/ha., it is one of the districts with the highest concentration of residents concerning the surface area of residential land built.

The 12 neighbourhoods of the Old Town have an uneven volume of the resident population, with the northeast quadrant of the district being the most populated area as opposed to the more southern and monumental neighbourhoods, which are less densely populated. As for the total number of residents registered by neighbourhoods, all in the Central District are above the average density of the city (98 inhabitants/ha.) except for Santa Cruz. However, the demographic vectors indicate a gradual decrease in the population in the last decade that exceeds 3.5%, and progressive ageing in the District, with a significant increase in the section of the population over 64 years old.

To represent the social conflict, a start has been made by mapping, based on the plots of land in Seville's Central District provided by the Seville City Council's Spatial Data Infrastructure (IDE), the sum of data showing the main elements of pressure on the local social fabric in this sector of the city. The District has been organised according to the sectors established in the Special Plan for the Protection of its Historical Ensemble (Seville City Council, 1994), which developed the 1987 General Urban Development Plan (Seville City Council, 1987), and which was incorporated as its own by the General Urban Development Plan renewed in 2006, still in force (Seville City Council, 2006).

For this purpose, the information provided by the Seville City Council's own Urban Planning Service IDE on the main indicators of commercial and tourist activity has been used first. This is how the data on restaurants, leisure establishments and bars were collected. Using geoprocessing tools, a density map of premises of this type was generated from a cloud of points representing each of the establishments, which was represented as a shaded area in Figure 1.

Fig.1 Representation of the density of restoration services and location of accommodation establishments in Seville Central District, together with the tourist attractions promoted by the local agency. Source: Authors (2020)

A layer of points corresponding to the location of hotel beds or tourist accommodation (individual or grouped) is superimposed on this same figure, obtained through three sources that have complemented each other for an exhaustive mapping:

- The georeferenced data on hotel and apartment establishments provided by the Spatial Data Infrastructure (IDE) of the Seville City Council
- The spatial data on tourist accommodations registered for rental in the area, provided by the company Airbnb through the web platform <http://insideairbnb.com/>.
- The spatial data on accommodation places in the area, both hotels and tourist accommodations and apartments, provided by the web platform of the booking company Booking

The results of the overlapping of the previous information for the area of the Central District of the city of Seville have been represented in Figure 1 and will be discussed in the following section.

After this, a more detailed case study has been undertaken of a specific area within the Central District in which, in addition to the density of accommodation and catering services for tourism, we will represent the tension with the traditional social fabric through changes in use in establishments open to the public. To this end, we have begun by establishing some criteria for their selection based on the results already obtained previously.

Firstly, the resident population in the different sectors of the district has been analysed, to select a study area in which there is still a high density of local inhabitants, which will allow us to map the social conflict, something that would not happen if we mapped an area in which the majority of homes have already been converted into tourist accommodation. In this sense, and according to the data provided by the Anuario Estadístico de Sevilla (Ayuntamiento de Sevilla, 2019), we will select a case study located in the northern sector of the Old Town.

Secondly, it will then be necessary to choose an area of sufficient size to extract a significant sample in cases of change, permanence or disappearance of traditional uses. From the map of the Central District already drawn up (Figure 1), the study is limited to those areas of the northern half of the district that show a significant density of both leisure and catering premises and tourist accommodation, restricting the possibilities to three areas: Santa Catalina-Puerta Osario, Alameda de Hércules-Feria, and Encarnación-Regina.

Among these, both the area of Alameda de Hércules (Díaz Parra, 2014; Díaz Parra & Jover, 2018) and the area around the Plaza de la Encarnación (González Sedano, 2009) have been previously studied both in terms of the effect of tourism and gentrification and in the transformation of traditional uses. For this

reason, the area of Santa Catalina-Puerta Osario was chosen as a case study on a detailed scale, interesting because it conserves a high density of local population, because it brings together a large number of leisure and restaurant establishments, shops and tourist accommodation, as well as being the natural exit from the historic centre to the Santa Justa Seville high-speed train station (AVE).

As for its delimitation, this has not been made to coincide with the sectors already determined by the aforementioned Special Plan for the Protection of the Historical Site of Seville, as it is considered that they respond to generally historical and morphological questions of the urban fabric, far from the interest of this work in social and tourist pressures. Thus, an area has been defined in which the concentration of catering and accommodation establishments was particularly dense, to have a representative sample for the study (Figures 2 and 3).

For this area, on-site data have been taken through fieldwork, previous knowledge and information provided by previous photographs from the Google Street View tool. A total of 166 establishments open to the public or with economic activity in the neighbourhood have been mapped. Three fields of study have been established for each one of them: the original use (before the growth of tourism in Seville, which, according to what was studied in the previous section, dates between 2013 and 2018, so we will establish a mid-point of reference in 2015), the current use (at the time this work is being completed) and the data that will be reflected on the map, which illustrates the effect of the citizen-tourist conflict on the public use of the city: whether the traditional use has been maintained, whether it has shifted to a tourist activity or whether it has been lost (i.e. the building is vacant). The latter category also includes residential buildings that are currently empty, as they are considered potential containers for public use, including hotel use or tourist accommodation. A summary of the results obtained may be consulted in Table 1.

Table 1. Changes of use by establishments in Santa Catalina-Puerta Osario area, Seville

Variable assigned to use	Number of establishments	Percentage of total mapped	Colour in the map (Fig. 2 and 3)
Traditional use maintained	101	61%	Yellow
Use changed to tourist activity	30	18%	Blue
Traditional use lost	35	21%	Purple

Source: Authors (2020)

To simplify the results and organize them for future research that could amplify this, the uses assigned have been limited to the following 10 types: housing, equipment, hotel, hostel, tourist accommodation, bar, restaurant, neighbourhood trade, tourist trade or vacant plot.

Fig.2 Cartography of the Santa Catalina-Puerta Osario case study, superimposing the changes in the use of public establishments on the density of tourist accommodation in the area. Source: Authors (2020)

Fig.3 Cartography of the Santa Catalina-Puerta Osario case study, superimposing the changes in the use of public establishments to the density of catering and leisure establishments in the area. Source: Authors (2020)

The results of the previous count have been mapped over the area chosen as a case study in two situations: overlapping it with the density of tourist accommodation -hotels, hostels and apartments for tourist renting- (Figure 2) and then overlapping it with the density of establishments open to the public -trades, leisure and restaurant- (Figure 3).

6. FINDINGS

First of all, the aim was to understand the extent of tourist action in the city centre of Seville and, more specifically, in its Central District. To this end, the most general, impartial and official source available was consulted: the promotional information provided by the Seville Tourism Agency on the Seville City Council's Tourism website. In it, a varied offer can be observed from the subject matter, offering options for all publics among which, without a doubt, the allusions to buildings and public spaces of a heritage nature stand out, so we can say that the tourist offer in Seville is fundamentally aimed at cultural heritage tourism. In addition to this, what fundamentally interests us at the level of results obtained in this section has been the proportion of urban elements and spaces that, of the total, are found in Seville's Central District: 80 per cent, which, together with the fact that currently, only 8.4 per cent of Seville's population lives in this area, gives an idea of the dimension of the conflict between citizens and tourists in the district and validates their choice as the object of study for this research.

This was followed by a study based on the newspaper library, official communications and public documents on the evolution of the conflict and how it has been dealt with by local administrations and the media. In light of the results, we can confirm that, although the first actions to contain the changes of use in public space, which arrived in 2013 with the creation of a noise map caused by restaurants and leisure establishments, with the consequent limitations for the development of these activities, it is not until very recently, in 2018, when the first actions by Seville City Council and citizen groups begin to take place in parallel. It has been noted that, during this time, the tension has been maintained, with very recent actions by both parties to the writing of this work. It is also observed how one of the main problems that focus the conflict is the problem in the right to housing in the Central District caused by the proliferation of tourist rental accommodation, which has had attempts to be regulated without results to date.

However, the main objective of this work was to represent the conflict by mapping the changes in use in the urban fabric of Seville's Central District. In this sense, the first phase was to establish some parameters to define the inhabitants of this area of the city based on official statistics, thanks to which it was concluded that the district still has a generally dense local population, although the most depopulated

areas are beginning to be those in the southern half, where most of the monumental elements that function as a first-level tourist attraction are also located.

After this, a map was drawn up based on the contrast between two of the factors that had been revealed as significant in the social conflict: the existence of catering and leisure premises, and the massive presence of tourist accommodation. By superimposing these two layers on the plots, it can be seen how, in general terms, there is a correlation between the densities of the two parameters. Furthermore, it can be seen that most of the saturated areas are in the southern area, while in the northern half there are three fundamental focal points: Encarnación-Campana, Alameda de Hércules-Feria and Santa Catalina-Puerta Osario. From these, the last location was chosen as a case to elaborate a detailed study, given the existence of other previous investigations on the rest of the areas.

The last phase of obtaining the results has been centred, therefore, in the area of the greater density of tourist accommodation and establishments open to the public in the surroundings of Santa Catalina-Puerta Osario, from which data have been taken on-site on the state and evolution of the original uses per plot in its mutation towards tourist appropriation. It is observed, in the first place, that most establishments (61%) still conserve their original use, while a good part has lost it (21%) and the same (18%) has mutated from traditional use to a tourist one. Among the latter, most are, by far, located in areas with the highest density of establishments open to the public -because they have become shops or restaurants for tourism- or with the highest amount of tourist accommodation -which are the object of the change of dwellings to this type of rental activity-. On the contrary, most of the lost uses, that is, stores and buildings that are currently empty, are located in the areas that are less dense in terms of establishments and accommodation, which may show us that tourist pressure is exercising, in addition to social conflict, a polarisation in the use of the land and in the distribution of traditional uses and inhabitants in the Central District which, in turn, would aggravate the conflict.

7. CONCLUSION

The research has contributed to the existing discussion on the spatial conflict derived from over-tourism, which leads to social conflict. It is shown how the tensions between the everyday needs and uses of the local population and the services and accommodation provided to tourism are reflected in the reactions of the administrations to regulate this process and among citizen groups that are beginning to demand that measures be taken to guarantee their right to the city and housing.

The data visualization has enabled the analysis of the variables involved in explaining the relationships that are established between citizens and their immediate environment. In this sense, the final construction

of cartographies reveals a relationship between the location of tourist attractions, the transformation of traditional uses into leisure and catering establishments and, at the same time and over the same areas, the emergence of short-term tourist rental accommodation. This mapping could serve as a basis for decision-making for the formulation of urban and tourism policies for the regeneration of sustainable historical areas that are consistent with the social fabric.

However, due to the constraints of available space, the study has had to be limited both in terms of subject matter and scope, which leaves room for a variety of future research, among which we could point out: the monitoring of the advance of the conflict at a social level and its institutional response or vice versa; the use of the specific data on the use of the plots already taken for this area, which would allow an in-depth analysis of the casuistry in the substitution and abandonment of each of the traditional uses; or the extension of the data collection on the change of use to other areas of the Central District, extended to the entire district or even to other areas of the city.

8. BIBLIOGRAPHY

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